

Annex I

Solar System

Annex to Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars

CONTENTS:

The annex *Solar System*, is addressing the question of defining the Solar System in adequation with the reflexion regarding the expansion of life, as addressed in *Kingmakers life's gateway to the stars*.

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Introduction

Here we define the Solar System (1), choose a strategy to elect an adequate definition of its boundaries (2), and precise these, spacewise (3), and timewise (4). The odds of major external interferences are evaluated against the one where the evolutionary path of the Sun is the main driver for the evolution of the system (5). A definition for the habitable zone (Hz) is selected, whose evolution with time shows that the Solar System timewises constitutes three distinct ecosystems, separated by cataclysmic events (6).

1 - Definition

According to Nasa: “Our Solar System consists of our star, the Sun, and everything bound to it by gravity — the planets Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune, dwarf planets such as Pluto, dozens of moons and millions of asteroids, comets and meteoroids.”¹

2 - Boundaries

The Solar System has an extension in space, and in time. Depending on the considered properties, various boundaries may exist. The boundaries of the Solar System admit multiple definitions, based on the influence of the Sun, it being from the point of view of magnetic field, solar wind, gravity, light, possibility of detection, or more². The solar wind approach, for example, leads to the identification of termination shock, heliosheath, heliopause, heliopause, hydrogen wall and bow shock, any of these, being an envisionable possibility for defining what is inside and what is outside of the Solar System.

¹ [1] [\(Nasa 2020\) Our Solar System in depth](#)

² By many aspects, this work is an attempt to identify the boundary of the causal influence possibly exerted by the Solar System originated life.

This thesis is addressing life as we know it, with regard to the Solar System limits, and the opportunities lying beyond these. The retained definition should be pertinent in this respect. One of the key properties for life as characterized³, its requirement for accessible energy. The Solar System indeed is a place where energy may be collected, and that can only be escaped with an input of energy. From this perspective, I here below propose that the area of the influence of the Sun's gravity with respect to the neighbouring stars is meaningful to define practical spatial boundaries for the Solar System, spatially and temporally. This translates in defining the Solar System as the envelope of the Sun and all celestial bodies gravitationally bound to the Sun.

3 - Space

When investigating gravity as a useful property to define the Solar System, I find three classes of solutions.

Known objects

A first one is to define the boundary of the Solar System, as the surface containing the trajectories of all known objects orbiting the Sun, directly or indirectly, at a given moment. The limitation of this class of solution is that objects are constantly discovered, that do orbit the Sun from larger and larger distances. To my knowledge, the farthest identified object as of today is the trans neptunian object 2017 MB7, about 80 UA away from the Sun, whose aphelion is calculated to range up to 3400AU (0.05ly)⁴.

Possible trajectories of possible objects

A second class of solution is to define the boundary of the Solar System, as the surface containing all the possible trajectories of the possible bodies orbiting the Sun, directly or indirectly, at a given moment. The issue with this definition is that the gravity field is dependent on the presence of the bodies themselves. When the entire collection of bodies is known, the problem is called a n-bodies problem, and is at the center of the investigations in celestial mechanics. To allow for the separation of gravitationally bound elements, the concept of a zero velocity surface is being used, that cannot be crossed by bodies below a certain amount of

³ See main document: III)A) Life: *“Life is evolving, self-reproducing, transducing energy and converting its substrate”*

⁴ [2]([Jet Propulsion Laboratory 2020](#)) [JPL Small-Body Database Browser](#)

energy. From this approach, a zero velocity surface, with respect to the stellar environment of the Sun, could be interpreted as a good candidate for our definition. As an approximation of this zero velocity surface, which has a complex and changing conformation, and whose calculation requires computational resources out of my reach here, the sphere of influence, or the Hills sphere of the Sun, with respect to the closest stellar neighbours, could be used as a proposed definition for a boundary to the Solar System.

The sphere of influence (SOI) of the Sun regarding another celestial structure, is the volume within which the gravitational influence of the Sun is overcoming the one of the other body:

$$\text{Influence sphere radius} = a * (m/M)^{2/5}$$

Where a is the semi major axis, m is the mass of the Sun, and M is the mass of the other considered body

The Hills sphere is an approximation of the volume within which a negligible mass will tend to become the satellite of the Sun, rather than the one of the other, more massive celestial structure.

$$\text{Hill sphere radius} = a * \sqrt[3]{(m/3M)}$$

Table 1. Radius of solar Hill sphere and SOI, with respect to the closest stellar system

Structure assessed	Semi-maj or axis (a), ly	Mass of object (M_{\odot})	Radius of the solar sphere of influence with respect to this structure (ly)	Radius of the solar sphere of Hill, with respect to this structure (ly)
Alpha Centauri system (3 star system), our closest system	4.37	2.10	3.25	2.37

Observed or hypothetical noticeable distributions

The last class of proposition is to define the boundary of the Solar System by a relevant distribution of observed or theoretical celestial bodies. The limit may be proposed to be the Kuiper belt, found as far as 30-55UA from the Sun. Constituted of a large amount of asteroids, comets and at least three dwarf planets : Pluto, Haumea and Makemake, it has a disk shape, and is confirmed by observation. Further out, the hypothetical disk shaped Hills cloud, located

The solar sphere of influence as a spatial boundary of the Solar System

Following the above analysis, the choice is made for the calculations and the discussion, to retain **3.25ly**, as the radius of the Sun SOI with respect to its closest stellar neighbour, Alpha Centauri, as the spatial boundary of the Solar System. With the chosen boundary, the Sun is the main gravitational influence regarding existing objects, and all known and hypothesized objects orbiting the Sun including the outermost Oort cloud, are contained within this boundary. From the point of view of living organisms, and of interstellar navigation, this also delineates the volume inside which energy is required for escaping the solar influence. This also connects with an easy representation, because 3.25ly is very close to a parsec (pc).

4 - Time

From the above definition, the chosen boundary is a function of the mass of the Solar System, and of the distance to its most proximate stellar neighbour. Both do change over time. Then from the point of view of life, accessible energy is critical.

Debuts

The Solar System is the product of the collapse of an interstellar molecular cloud, 4.6 Billion years ago.

Mass

The Sun itself represents 99.8% of the total mass of the system⁵. During the main sequence, we will consider that the mass exchanges with the outside are negligible⁶, as well as the mass lost through nuclear conversion to energy through the fusion of H into He during the main

⁵ [1] ([Nasa 2020](#)) [Our Solar System in depth](#)

⁶ Even when considering the ejection of entire planets, as envisioned in [Expelled materials](#)

sequence⁷, this until the the core hydrogen has entirely been converted into He, turns into a red giant 7Gy from now, a time at which 33% of the mass will be lost through a stellar wind⁸

Neighbours

As a consequence, during the main sequence, the principal factor to the evolution of the Solar boundary, is the relative proximity of stellar neighbours. With calculated trajectories, such as the one of the Sholtz star, closing to less than 0.8ly to the Sun, which is five time closer than the closest star today, and a frequency of such events calculated to be of about one every 9 Million years⁹, it appears that reductions by as much as 50% of the radius of what may be considered as the Solar System are probably recurrent, and possibly meaningful as far as the possibilities for interstellar travel are concerned.

>> The spatial boundaries of the Solar System are wobbling with stars passing-by, and reducing with its progressive loss of mass.

Table 2. Reduction of the solar SOI with respect to stars flying by

Star or System	Minimal distance during flyby (ly)	Mass of Object (M_{\odot})	Radius of the Solar sphere of influence with respect to this structure (ly)
70.000 years ago (Scholz's star)	0.8	0.095	2.05
30.000 years in the future (Alpha Centauri system)	3	2.1	2.23

Better than traveling to the stars: let them travel to you. Barnard's star (6ly away, flyby 10.000years ahead), Ross248 (10ly, flyby in 35.000years), and Gliese 445(17ly, flyby in 48.000years), will come closer than todays distance to Proxima Centauri (4.2ly).

5 - The end

With boundaries set as proposed above, over long ranges of times, the interactions with other celestial bodies and planetary systems may lead to different futures. After considering the exotic futures where the main drivers for the history of the system are external interference, we will

⁷ [3] ([Stanford SOLAR Center 2020](#)) About 0.034% of the Solar Mass:

⁸ [4] ([Schröder and Connors 2008](#)) [Distant future of the Sun and Earth revisited](#)

⁹ [5] ([Mamajek et al. 2015](#)) [The closest known flyby of a star to the solar system](#)

Exotic futures

The Solar System could well merge, collide, or exchange large quantities of materials with another system.

Stellar threats

An average of one stellar system is calculated to pass within the defined Solar System (3.25ly Radius, today) every 83.000 years¹⁰. Should this rate be maintained, a strong assumption that would require further investigation, the 15 billions years¹¹ of possible habitability of the Solar System would see an integrated total to 136.000 stellar systems flying *through the Solar System*. Inducing mutual interactions, exchanges or collisions. The distance, inside the Solar System, at which the flyby would be cataclysmic, may be debated. In my opinion, there is little doubt that whatever the oncourse system, a flyby closer than the Kuiper belt would have cataclysmic consequences. The above numbers leads to to a probability of such a cataclysm of about 1% per billion year

Galactic threats

M31 galaxy (Andromeda, one trillion stars), then M33 Galaxy(40 billion stars), for a total of 1040 million stars, are bound to collide with the Milky Way, collisions which are envisioned as the next major cosmic events, and which are predictable with some certainty, leading to an estimate for a merger with M31 in 5.86 (+1.61-0.72) Gyr from now (during the Sun red giant phase), and with M33 within the 10Gyr to come¹². These events, from the Solar System perspective, may be understood as the providers of an increased stellar threat, as proposed above.

Exotic possibilities

Exotic possibilities are endless, ranging from a simple orbit alteration for a planet, to comet shower related to the disturbance of the Oort cloud, to life bricks or lifeforms hopping from one system to the other, to the gravitational binding of stars potentially leading to supernovas, not forgetting the low but existing probability of frontal collisions. It is obvious that within that range of options, dissertation on the future of the Solar System “without external disturbances” might seem idealistic. Still, even multiplying arbitrarily by 2 the above cataclysmic encounter rate (1%/GY), as an attempt for accounting for the merger with M31-M33, the probability is led to be

¹⁰ [6] [\(García-Sánchez et al. 2001\) Stellar encounters with the solar system](#)

¹¹ See below “synthesis on habitability”

¹² [7] [\(van der Marel et al. 2012\) The M31 Velocity Vector. III. Future Milky Way-M31-M33...](#)

of 70% over the 15Gy of habitability, that nothing cataclysmic happen. The “conventional” fate is worth investigation.

Conventional future

The exchanges between the Solar System and the galactic environment could be relatively insignificant, and the system be left globally as is today, with the Sun as its unique star. The Sun is a main sequence star, converting hydrogen to helium. When exiting this main sequence, the Sun will start burning helium, and turn into a red giant, expanding to engulf all the inner planets, and possibly Earth, within an accelerated expansion happening 5-7 billion years from now. It will then suddenly contract, and enter a series of pulses leading to an explosion as a planetary nebula. Eventually, our star will collapse into a white dwarf, 50% of the mass of the actual Sun, whose luminosity will only be fueled by the remaining thermal energy, eventually cooling down.

6 - Habitable zone

Multiple definitions exist regarding habitable zone¹³(HZ), and what has mainly been investigated relates to “biological life as we know it”. Life as we do not know it, ie artificial, or extraterrestrial biological life, might have absolutely different environmental constraints, some hypothesis even leading to the conclusion that artificial, silicon based life, would favor near zero kelvin temperature due to the increased efficiency at these temperatures¹⁴. In the below discussion, the habitable zone is defined as the volume within which liquid water may exist at the surface of celestial bodies, a volume which shall consequentially be understood as the lower bound for where life, generally speaking, may develop or be sustained.

Main sequence phase: birth of the Solar System to + 5.4Gy total duration = 10Gy

Calculated as such, a conservative estimate, leads to the habitable zone to range from 0.95 AU to 1.37 AU, with these boundaries evolving proportionally to the square root of the solar luminosity¹⁵. The habitable zone is gradually shifting outbound, by a factor of two, with the progressive increase of the Sun's luminosity.

Red giant phase: 5.4Gy - 7.6Gy total duration = 2.2Gy

¹³ [8] (Ed. Gerda Horneck & Christa Baumstark-Khan 2002) [Astrobiology - the quest for the cond...p47](#)

¹⁴ [9] (Sandberg et al. 2017) [That is not dead which can eternal lie: aestivation hypothesis...](#)

¹⁵ [4] (Schröder and Connors 2008) [Distant future of the Sun and Earth revisited](#)

About 5Gy from now, core hydrogen will be exhausted, and the Sun will enter its red giant phase, where its radius and luminosity will increase more and more quickly while its mass loses 30%, to a stage where the radius of the Sun is increased by about 200, to possibly approach or engulf Earth orbit, depending of studies.

As species migrate north when climate heats up, life might migrate to the outer regions within the Solar System, such as the Kuiper belt, which, being in the habitable zone of the future red giant, may stand as survivable, and does comprehend 10^5 bodies of diameters superiors to 50km, equating to a total surface superior to three time the surface of the terrestrial planets¹⁶. Such a translation could happen naturally through exchanges of materials with collisions and ejections¹⁷, by the means of spaceships, or as proposed by some authors, by changing the orbits of habitable planets or structures to follow the habitable zone outwards. Regarding Earth, Korycansky, Laughlin & Adams (2001), have proposed the selective alteration of asteroids orbits to collision courses, so as to induce the orbit change. One crash would be required every 6000 years, to collect the required energy, in their scenario.

Core helium flash: 7.6Gy total duration = a flash then 120My of uncertainties

The red giant phase is ended by the sudden fusion of the core helium into carbon. During this process of exponential nature called the helium flash, 40% of the mass is converted, the release rate of energy is increased by 100 billion, to a total of about $5E+41J$ ¹⁸, and the Sun gets temporarily more luminous than its entire host galaxy¹⁹. Following the cataclysmic event, the radius and luminosity of the Sun are suddenly reduced by factors of 50(Luminosity), and 20(radius)²⁰. Following the helium flash, helium continues to be burnt, in what is referred to as an horizontal phase, calculated to be of about 100My for the Sun, until a new accelerated growth happens. Thermal pulsations initiate, to size and luminosity that are being debated, up until a final explosion into a planetary nebula along which 20% of the remaining mass is expelled, leaving behind a white dwarf. The planetary nebula itself is discussed and not certain, while the white dwarf is.²¹

¹⁶ [10] [\(Stern and Alan Stern 2003\) Delayed Gratification Habitable Zones...](#)

¹⁷ See [Expelled materials](#)

¹⁸ [11] [\(Edwards 1969\)The Hydrodynamics of the Helium Flash](#)

¹⁹ [12] [\(Deupree and Wallace 1987, page 731\) The Core Helium Flash...](#)

²⁰ Table below

²¹ [4] [\(Schröder and Cannon Smith 2008\) Distant future of the Sun and Earth revisited](#)

From the perspective of continued, life three issues arise: the first is the survival to the cataclysmic energy release, which seem highly improbable, the second, is the required relocation, following the shrinking of the habitable zone from 50-70 AU to initially 7 -10 AU²², and its further pulsations due the varying luminosity. The third is the existence of celestial bodies on which to relocate, which might simply not exist anymore, or might have been striped out of the necessary elements for survival.

While further work on the survivability of helium itself is required, the survivability of the post helium horizontal phase is proposed by some authors, that could last up to 1Gy, at distances 7-22 AU from the star, consistent with our calculations. With its short length and its position in between two cataclysmic events: the helium flash, and the planetary nebula, I propose this period of 0.1-1Gy could be referred to as a solar “eye” of the cyclone.

White dwarf phase 7.6Gy duration = +++

Resulting from the asymptotic giant, the remaining white dwarf is calculated to have a temperature of about 100,000K and to contain 54% of the Sun present mass, the rest of it having been lost to the interstellar medium²³. White dwarfs, such as our Sun beyond 7.7Gy, stand to the research community, as very likely to host life, and are motivating a dedicated use of Kepler spacecraft telescope time²⁴. The white dwarf used in the paper in reference is particularly interesting, because with $M = 0.6M_{\odot}$, $R = 0.01R_{\odot}$, and $L = 10-4L_{\odot}$, it happens to share the properties the post apocalyptic Sun, and the presented habitable zone may be used to infer the habitability of around the Sun once it will have turned into a white dwarf.

The habitable zone will progressively reduce with the luminosity of the star, from the range 0.03-0.06AU, millions of years after the planetary nebula, to 0.005-0.015, 7Gy years later (15Gy from now).

The remark may be made that these are extremely short orbital distances, leading to extremely short orbits, which in the ultimate moments of habitability will lower to years, lasting only 5 hours, which leads to several issues.

First is that this ultimate required proximity to the star is what sets the limit for habitability of the Solar System: Below 0.005 ly, the Roche limit is reached, for earth-density planets, which would suffer tidal dislocation.

²² Author's calculations, from the simple luminosity defined habitable zone as presented above.

²³ [13] (Lopez et al. 2005) Evolution of the Habitable Zone and Search for Life Around Red Giant Stars...

²⁴ [14] (Kilic et al. 2013) Habitable Planets Around White Dwarfs...

Then the question arises whether natural debris or planets may be orbiting at such distances, which actually lie way inside the radius of the proceedingly exploding asymptotic giant. While the red giant phase will have destructed planets located below 1AU²⁵, (hence probably Earth), any support for life in the short orbit habitable zone should either form there, or migrate from the outside, scenarios that are being envisioned by researchers. Evidences are met, thanks to observed short orbit planets orbiting post main sequence stars, such as KIC 05807616 or V391 Pegasi, that confirm the actual happening of such a process. The remaining giants may populate this inner habitable zone with asteroids and planets smaller than Earth. More, it appears that the process leading to this population is likely to lead to a heavy bombardment phase capable of delivering water and volatiles in the planet.²⁶

²⁵ [15,16] ([Silvotti et al. 2007, page 189](#); [Villaver and Livio 2007, page 449](#)) [A giant planet orbiting the 'extreme horizontal branch' star V 391 Pegasi / Can planets survive stellar evolution ?](#)

²⁶ [17] ([Loeb and Maoz 2013, page 432](#)) [Detecting biomarkers in habitable-zone...](#)

Synthesis

The choice is made to retain **3.25ly**, as the radius of the Sun sphere of influence (SOI), with respect to its closest stellar neighbour, Alpha Centauri, as the spatial boundary of the Solar System. Because it is dependent on the mass of the Solar System, of the one of the most proximate neighbor, and of the distance between these, the sphere of influence is wobbling with stellar systems flying by, and progressively reducing due to the ejection of solar winds, and to the conversion of matter to energy. With the chosen boundary, the Sun is the main gravitational influence regarding existing objects, and all known and hypothesized objects orbiting the Sun including the outermost Oort cloud, are contained within this boundary. From the point of view of living organisms, and of interstellar navigation, this limit also delineates the volume inside which energy is required for escaping the solar influence. This also connects with an easy representation, because 3.25ly is very close to a parsec (pc).

From the perspective of survivability, three main continuous periods have then to be distinguished, separated in time by cataclysmic events, problematic for any lifeform to survive, but between which new ecosystems could develop in an habitable zone when defined by liquid surface water, which we will consider as a good proxy for discussion the survival of life as we know it:

- **Solar System 1.0:** the one we are living in, where life will be sustainable for 7 another billion years or so provided it migrates outbound with an accelerating pace, from the current 0.8-1.1 AU Habitable zone, across to the extreme limits of the Kuiper belt, following the growth of the Sun as a red giant. Solar System 1.0 is doomed to a cataclysmic end due the helium flash, resetting the habitable zone back to 7-20 AU.
- **Solar System 2.0: the eye of the cyclone,** a short period ranging between 0.1 and 1Gy, in between the helium flash, and the pulsing phase of the asymptotic giant.
- **Solar System 3.0:** where life will be sustainable for further billions of years, should there be a celestial body or support for it, within a smaller slowly shrinking habitable zone, lasting 7 billion years and ultimately bounded by the tidal disruption due to the proximity of the star, when the habitable zone surface freezing limit is reduced to about 0.005AU.

Figure 1, proposed below, synthesizes those three phases, alongside with the discussed properties with the corresponding movements of the habitable zone.

Fig 1. The three main phases for the habitable zone in the Solar System

With the surface liquid water criteria, separated by cataclysmic events

Note: according to the above simple estimation, over the 15Gyr ahead, this scenario holds a +70-85% probability, the 15-30% remaining being a wide range of possible exotic futurs, driven by interactions with other stellars systems, amplified, 5.8Gyr ahead, by the merger with M31 then M33 galaxy.

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